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Controlling Amplitude of Guitar String Vibrations

Bachelor's Thesis

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Abstract

This thesis deals with the physics and design of electromagnetic string drivers for electric guitars. Those hand-held or built-in devices enable guitarists to initiate and sustain vibrations without plucking the string. Of further musical importance is that these devices enable to alter the dynamics of a single musical note, which is not possible for unaugmented plucked string instruments.

The generic model of the electromagnetic actuator (and its sensor counterpart) as well as model limitations are presented in section 2.1. This is followed by guitar specific observations regarding the transducer efficiency in sections 2.2 and 2.3. The analysis is focused on the number of windings, the core's material and level of magnetic polarization as well as the core's geometry. Experiments (subsec. 2.2.2) confirmed the theoretical result, that to a certain number of windings, the actuator efficiency is proportional to the number of windings. From there on, actuator efficiency is independent of the number of windings. For the sensor, increasing the number of windings will always increase the induced voltage and thus transducer efficiency. The presented "E"-shaped core geometry reduces the magnetic reluctance of the system and showed a 25% increase in induced sensor voltage.

The behaviour of the closed feedback loop - string, sensor, electronic amplifier, actuator, string - is analyzed in chapter 3. Solving the corresponding differential equation yields the influence of the amplifier gain on the decay constant as well as the necessary phase relation between actuator and sensor signal. In order to achieve positive feedback the sensor signal needs to be amplified in phase, for negative feedback it needs to be inverted. Experiments with a closed feedback loop (sec. 3.3) confirmed these results.

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1. Introduction

Acoustic and electric guitars are among the most played musical instruments in the western world. Some reasons might be that the guitar is an affordable and portable harmony instrument, well established in many musical genres. However, compared to melodic instruments like the trumpet or the violin, guitars lack one basic means of expression. Once the string is plucked, there is no way to modify the dynamics of the musical note. A crescendo or decrescendo can only be played from note to note, but not within a single note. The natural decrescendo of a guitar note can only be further accelerated by the player (damping the vibration with his hand), but can never be stopped or even inverted into a crescendo.

These limitations have led to inventions like the commercially available 'EBow' (electronic bow for guitar), patented by Gregory Heet in 1978 [4]. The EBow is a hand-held device to excite and sustain string vibrations on electric guitars (generally speaking, any instrument with ferromagnetic strings). Its function is based on three components: input coil (sensor), amplifier, output coil (driver/actuator) (seen in figure 1.1).

The input coil acts like a regular guitar pickup, transducing the mechanical vibration into an electrical signal. The signal, consisting of the fundamental and harmonic frequencies, is then amplified electrically. The output of the amplifier is connected to a second coil that produces an alternating magnetic field (electromagnet). Only if the ferromagnetic string is constantly magnetized by a permanent magnet, the alternating field will cause an alternating force acting on the string.

The EBow finally allowed guitarists to manipulate the dynamics of a musical note and create flute or violin like sounds on a guitar. Though it opens up new musical possibilities, unfortunately, it does cancel existing ones. The fact that it is hand-held means that one either plays using the device **or** the well-trained plucking techniques (using fingers or a plectrum). In contrast to

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Figure 1.1.: Basic components of a magnetic string driver.

Figure 1.2.: Guide grooves align the EBow. [7]

a hand-held magnetic feedback device like the EBow, plucking techniques enable instant attack and fast changes of the played string. Because the EBow works best resting on the two adjacent strings of the excited string, attempts of fast string crossings can produce unwanted scratching noise (figure 1.2).

Holding the EBow in such a way that the string can also be plucked with a plectrum can become quite uncomfortable and doesn't prevent scratching noise while crossing strings (fig. 1.3).

A technical solution that enables to combine the extended means of expression with unaffected traditional playing techniques seems interesting, but is not available on the market. In fact, permanently installed magnetic

Figure 1.3.: Combination of picking technique and EBow. [7]

resonators are available (Sustainiac[®] or Fernandes Sustainer[™]), but their feedback is static and results in endless sustain rather than enhanced dynamic control. The complete development of an installed dynamic feedback system would go way beyond the scope of a bachelor's thesis. Therefore, this thesis investigates the underlying physics of an electromechanical feedback loop as seen in magnetic string drivers. Design suggestions are made and, as far as possible, verified by experiments with prototypes.

The thesis is divided into two chapters, the first one dealing with the electromagnetic actuator and sensor as individual electromechanical systems. The second chapter examines the closed feedback loop including the electronic amplifier.

2. Electromagnetic Actuator and Sensor

In subsection 2.1.1 the generic two-port model of an electromagnetic transducer will be derived. With the aid of mechanical-electrical analogies, it is possible to construct an analogous electrical circuit model. This simplifies the application of circuit analysis methods and allows simulating the system's behaviour via SPICE software. However, the applicability of the model to guitar string drivers is limited, which will be discussed in subsection 2.1.2.

The guitar-specific design and practical evaluation of actuator prototypes is the topic of section 2.2, followed by section 2.3 dealing with the sensor design and evaluation.

2.1. Model of an Electromagnetic Transducer

2.1.1. Generic Model

A magnetic transducer is a special case of an electromechanical transducer that, generally speaking, transforms electrical signals (voltage \underline{U} , current \underline{I}) into mechanical vibrations (velocity \underline{v} , force \underline{F}) and vice versa. The function of the magnetic transducer can be analyzed by means of the model seen in figure 2.1.

The components that form the magnetic transducer are core (1), armature (2) and the air gaps (3) in between the two.

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Figure 2.1.: Model of a magnetic transducer with operating point adjustment by means of a direct current or a permanent magnet. [1]

(1) Core:

The core is fixed and has a cross sectional area A . The coil of N windings (wire diameter d) is wound around the core. The core material must be ferro- or ferrimagnetic with a high relative magnetic permeability of $\mu_{Fe} \gg 1$. Within the core, a permanent magnet is placed and induces a static flux Φ_0 (flux density B_0). For the generic model, the magnet's material is supposed to have an equally high permeability $\mu_{mag} \gg 1$ as the rest of the core. This is only given in the case of a magnet material that is far from its maximum polarization.

(2) Armature:

The movable (vibrating) piece is generally called armature and must be made out of ferro- or ferrimagnetic material ($\mu_{Fe} \gg 1$). The rectangle on the right-hand side of the figure symbolizes the armature modeled as a damped oscillator with mass m , stiffness s and frictional resistance R_m . In this generic model the armature has the same cross sectional area A as the core. In the special application of this thesis, the vibrating armature will later be the guitar string.

(3) Air gaps:

The length of the air gaps is modulated during vibration ($x = x_0 + x_{\sim}$). Because air has a much lower relative magnetic permeability ($\mu_a \approx 1$) than ferro/ferrimagnetic materials ($\mu_{Fe} \gg 1$), the air gaps determine the overall

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magnetic reluctance of the magnetic series circuit composed out of core, air gaps and armature.

The function of the actuator relies on the physical phenomenon that a force is exerted on ferromagnetic material that is exposed to a magnetic field. The external field aligns the "elementary magnets" within the ferromagnetic piece and draws it into the field, no matter which magnetic pole comes close to the ferromagnetic piece. Both the permanent magnet and the electromagnet can cause a magnetic flux Φ that will exert a force F on the armature. Figure 2.2 shows an air gap like it is assumed for the generic model of the magnetic transducer. The length of the air gap l_0 is assumed to be small compared to the core's and armature's diameter. Thus, the effect of fringing is negligible and the flux density B (as well as the energy density w_{mag}) can be assumed constant in every point of the enclosed air volume. The magnetic energy W_{mag} stored within the initial air volume is then given as [1]:

$$W_{mag} = w_{mag} A l_0 = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} A l_0 \quad (2.1)$$

The constant μ_0 denotes the permeability of free space. A virtual displacement causes a change in energy ΔW_{mag} :

$$W_{mag} + \Delta W_{mag} = w_{mag} A (l_0 + \Delta l) = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} A l_0 + \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} A \Delta l \quad (2.2)$$

The change in energy ΔW_{mag} relates to the required force:

$$\Delta W_{mag} = F \cdot \Delta l \rightarrow F = \frac{\Delta W_{mag}}{\Delta l} = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} A \quad (2.3)$$

Because of the quadratic relation between force and magnetic field, an alternating field alone (created via the electromagnet) results in a pulling force at double the frequency of the actuator signal:

$$B_{\sim} = \hat{B} \sin(\omega t) \rightarrow B_{\sim}^2 = \hat{B}^2 \sin^2(\omega t) = \hat{B}^2 \frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos(2\omega t)) \quad (2.4)$$

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Figure 2.2.: Force between two nearby magnetized surfaces: initial state (left) and virtual displacement (right). [1]

$$F_{\sim} = B_{\sim}^2 \cdot \frac{A}{2\mu_0} = \hat{B}^2 \frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos(2\omega t)) \cdot \frac{A}{2\mu_0} \quad (2.5)$$

Since the exerted force should be of the same frequency as the induced electrical signal (linearity), this is undesirable. To solve this problem, the armature needs to be constantly magnetized by a permanent magnet, whose flux density B_0 is much larger than the alternating flux density of the electromagnet. Only then, the electromagnet can push and pull on the armature. If the actuating frequency is close to the resonance frequency of the armature (damped oscillator), the alternating displacements will be much larger than the bias displacement caused by the permanent magnet, although the field of the permanent magnet is stronger.

For the derivation of linear transducer equations, it is necessary to consider the constant field as a linearization of the otherwise quadratic relation between force and magnetic field/current. The linearization as well as the transducer equations will now be derived, leading to a two-port model of the magnetic transducer (referring mainly to [10]).

Assuming the air gaps to be short compared to the core diameter, we find a series circuit of magnetic reluctances all leading one and the same flux Φ (leakage flux is negligible). The cross sectional area of the core and armature shall be the same (A), thus the flux density B is constant along the circuit ($\Phi = B \cdot A$). Considering the relation $H(\mu) = B/\mu$ for a constant B -field and significantly differing permeabilities ($\mu_{Fe}, \mu_{mag} \gg \mu_a$) yields a vanishing H -field inside core and armature compared to the H -field in the air gap. Applying Ampere's law gives

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$$\oint \vec{H}(l) d\vec{l} = \underbrace{H_{Fe}}_{\approx 0} \cdot l_{Fe} + \underbrace{H_{mag}}_{\approx 0} \cdot l_{mag} + H_{air} \cdot l_{air} \approx H_{air} \cdot l_{air} = N \cdot I \quad (2.6)$$

, where $l_{air} = 2 \cdot x_0$ denotes the length of both air gaps. Combining this result with equation 2.3 leads to the overall force acting on the armature:

$$F = 2 \cdot \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} A = \mu_0 A H_{air}^2 = \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 I^2}{4x_0^2} \quad (2.7)$$

The constant field B_0 could equivalently be induced by a direct current I_0 . The overall current is then given by $I = I_0 + I_{\sim}$ leading to:

$$F = F_0 + F_{\sim} = \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 (I_0 + I_{\sim})^2}{4x_0^2} = \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 (I_0^2 + 2I_0 I_{\sim} + I_{\sim}^2)}{4x_0^2} \quad (2.8)$$

Since one is interested in the small-signal behaviour around the operating point F_0 , we continue without the DC component I_0^2 . The ratio

$$\frac{I_{\sim}^2}{2I_0 I_{\sim}} = \frac{I_{\sim}}{2I_0} \quad (2.9)$$

corresponds to the error in linearity. We assume the DC component to be much larger (neglecting the I_{\sim}^2 term) and end up with the linearized, small-signal transducer equation:

$$F_{\sim} = \mu_0 A \frac{2N^2 I_0 I_{\sim}}{4x_0^2} = \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 I_0 I_{\sim}}{2x_0^2} \quad (2.10)$$

Furthermore, this can be converted into permanent magnet operation by substituting I_0 :

$$\Phi_0 = B_0 \cdot A = \mu_0 H_0 \cdot A = \mu_0 \frac{N I_0}{2x_0} \cdot A \rightarrow I_0 = \frac{\Phi_0 \cdot 2x_0}{\mu_0 N A} \quad (2.11)$$

2. Electromagnetic Actuator and Sensor

$$F_{\sim} = \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 I_0 I_{\sim}}{2x_0^2} = \frac{N\Phi_0}{x_0} \cdot I_{\sim} = \alpha \cdot I_{\sim} \quad (2.12)$$

Regarding the sensor function, the mechanical vibration of the armature is transformed into a corresponding electrical signal. A vibration means that the length of the air gap is varying ($x = x_0 - x_{\sim}$). This modulation of the magnetic reluctance R_{mag} leads to a modulation of the magnetic flux Φ , since the magnetomotive force Θ (permanent magnet) remains unchanged ($\Theta = \Phi \cdot R_{mag}$). The induced voltage at the open terminals of the coil shall now be calculated:

$$\Phi = \mu_0 H(x) A = \mu_0 \frac{NI_0}{2x} A = \mu_0 \frac{NI_0}{2(x_0 - x_{\sim})} A \quad (2.13)$$

$$U_{\sim} = N \cdot \frac{d\Phi}{dt} = \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 I_0}{2} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{1}{x_0 - x_{\sim}} \right) = \quad (2.14)$$

$$= \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 I_0}{2} \left(-\frac{1}{(x_0 - x_{\sim})^2} \right) \cdot \left(-\frac{dx_{\sim}}{dt} \right) = \quad (2.15)$$

$$= \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 I_0}{2} \frac{1}{x_0^2 - 2x_0 x_{\sim} + x_{\sim}^2} \cdot v_{\sim} \quad \text{with } \frac{dx_{\sim}}{dt} = v_{\sim} \quad (2.16)$$

If the change in air gap length x_{\sim} is small compared to the bias length x_0 , one can neglect the x_{\sim} terms in the denominator of the fractional. Moreover, I_0 can be substituted as derived in equation 2.11:

$$U_{\sim} = \mu_0 A \frac{N^2 I_0}{2} \frac{1}{x_0^2} \cdot v_{\sim} = \frac{N\Phi_0}{x_0} \cdot v_{\sim} = \alpha \cdot v_{\sim} \quad (2.17)$$

Writing the two transducer equations in phasor and matrix notation, one obtains a compact mathematical description of the ideal magnetic transducer:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_i \\ \underline{I}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha \\ 1/\alpha & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{F}_i \\ \underline{v}_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.18)$$

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Figure 2.3.: Two-port model of the ideal magnetic transducer. [10]

It is convenient to separate this two-port into two cascaded two-ports (figure 2.3). One, that formally transforms the mechanical into electrical units (and vice versa) by means of a constant N_I with $[N_I] = \frac{N}{A}$ (force-current-analogy) and a second electrical "correcting two-port" that takes account of the specific transducer constant α . Observing figure 2.3 one finds:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_i \\ \underline{I}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha \\ 1/\alpha & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{E}_i \\ \underline{v}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha/N_I & 0 \\ 0 & N_I/\alpha \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & N_I \\ 1/N_I & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{E}_i \\ \underline{v}_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.19)$$

The "correcting two-port"-matrix is the one of an ideal transformer with $u = \alpha/N_I$ ("winding ratio").

The full and real model adds the coil (winding resistance R_c , inductance L_c) as well as the damped oscillator (armature/guitar string, figure 2.4). Obviously a single damped oscillator can only model one mode of vibration of the string. In this thesis it will always correspond to the fundamental mode/frequency.

By multiplying the three chain matrices (coil, ideal magnetic transducer, damped oscillator) one obtains the chain matrix of the real magnetic transducer. Given the coil's impedance $\underline{Z}_c = R_c + j\omega L_c$ its chain matrix results to:

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Figure 2.4.: Two-port model of the real magnetic transducer. [10]

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{U} \\ \underline{I} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \underline{Z}_c \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_i \\ \underline{I}_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.20)$$

The ideal transducer matrix has been derived to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_i \\ \underline{I}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha \\ 1/\alpha & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{F}_i \\ \underline{v}_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.21)$$

The mechanical impedance of the damped oscillator $\underline{Z}_{m,O} = R_m + j\omega m + \frac{s}{j\omega}$ gives the following chain matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{F}_i \\ \underline{v}_i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \underline{Z}_{m,O} \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{F} \\ \underline{v} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.22)$$

As mentioned, multiplication of these three matrices yields the electromechanical chain matrix of the real magnetic transducer:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{U} \\ \underline{I} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \underline{Z}_c \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \alpha \\ 1/\alpha & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \underline{Z}_{m,O} \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{F} \\ \underline{v} \end{bmatrix} = \quad (2.23)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\alpha} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{Z}_c & \alpha^2 + \underline{Z}_c \cdot \underline{Z}_{m,O} \\ 1 & \underline{Z}_{m,O} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \underline{F} \\ \underline{v} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.24)$$

2.1. Model of an Electromagnetic Transducer

The output port of the mechanical oscillator two port (\underline{F} , \underline{v}) remains open-circuited as the sound radiation from the vibrating string is neglected. This corresponds to neglecting the acoustical load (radiation impedance) of the air surrounding the string. It follows that the force \underline{F} is zero. Inserting $\underline{F} = 0$ into equation 2.24 simplifies it significantly:

$$\underline{U} = \alpha \cdot \underline{v} + \underline{Z}_c \cdot \frac{\underline{Z}_{m,O} \cdot \underline{v}}{\alpha} = \alpha \cdot \underline{v} + \underline{Z}_c \cdot \frac{\underline{F}_{m,O}}{\alpha} = \quad (2.25)$$

$$= \alpha \cdot \underline{v} + \underline{Z}_c \cdot \frac{\underline{F}_i - \underline{F}}{\alpha} = \alpha \cdot \underline{v} + \underline{Z}_c \cdot \frac{\underline{F}_i}{\alpha} = \alpha \cdot \underline{v} + \underline{Z}_c \cdot \underline{I}_i = \quad (2.26)$$

$$= \alpha \cdot \underline{v} + \underline{Z}_c \cdot \underline{I} \quad (2.27)$$

$$\underline{I} = \frac{\underline{Z}_{m,O} \cdot \underline{v}}{\alpha} = \frac{\underline{F}_{m,O}}{\alpha} \quad (2.28)$$

Equation 2.27 yields that for the real transducer, the voltage drop across the coil ($\underline{Z}_c \cdot \underline{I}$), corresponding to dissipative (R_c) and reactive (L_c) power, is taken into account. Equally important for later observations is equation 2.28: The electrical input current \underline{I} is not only proportional to, but also in phase with the mechanical force $\underline{F}_{m,O}$ exerting the string's vibration.

By choosing $N_I = \alpha$ the transformer two-port can be left away, since $u = \alpha/N_I = \alpha/\alpha = 1$. The mechanical impedances (\underline{Z}_m) are transformed into equivalent electrical impedances (\underline{Z}_e) by means of the force-current unit transducer, again using $N_I = \alpha$ [10]:

$$\underline{Z}_m = \frac{\underline{F}}{\underline{v}} = \frac{N_I \cdot \underline{I}}{\underline{U}/N_I} = \frac{\alpha \cdot \underline{I}}{\underline{U}/\alpha} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\underline{Z}_e} \quad (2.29)$$

$$j\omega m = \alpha^2 j\omega C \quad \rightarrow \quad C = \frac{m}{\alpha^2} \quad (2.30)$$

$$\frac{s}{j\omega} = \frac{\alpha^2}{j\omega L} \quad \rightarrow \quad L = \frac{\alpha^2}{s} \quad (2.31)$$

$$R_m = \frac{\alpha^2}{R} \quad \rightarrow \quad R = \frac{\alpha^2}{R_m} \quad (2.32)$$

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Figure 2.5.: Electrical two-port model of the real magnetic transducer. [10]

The inductance L_c can be calculated by combining equation 2.6 with $\Phi = L \cdot I/N$.

$$L_c = \frac{N \cdot \Phi}{I} = \frac{N \cdot \mu_0 H \cdot A}{I} = \frac{\mu_0 N^2 A}{2x_0} \quad (2.33)$$

The series resistance R_c is defined by the length l and diameter d of the wire as well as the electrical resistivity ρ of the wire material:

$$R_c = \frac{\rho \cdot l}{A} = \frac{\rho \cdot l}{\pi \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2} \quad (2.34)$$

Figure 2.5 shows the analogous electrical model of the magnetic transducer that will be specified for the guitar string arrangement and simulated with SPICE in the following subsection. Since the terminals of the electromechanical unit transducer are open-circuited, it can simply be left away for the simulation. However, to convert electrical into mechanical quantities, one should always be aware of the transducer constant α .

2.1.2. Limited Application to Guitar String Drivers

Figure 2.6 schematically shows an actuator-string arrangement similar to the presented model.

One central assumption of the model was that the magnetic reluctance is determined by the air gaps x_0 , because the rest of the magnetic circuit is

2.1. Model of an Electromagnetic Transducer

Figure 2.6.: Actuator-string arrangement.

composed of highly permeable ($\mu_{Fe}, \mu_{mag} \gg 1$) and magnetically unsaturated material. An electric guitar string is made of steel (high permeability), but will saturate very quickly. An approximately constant static flux Φ_0 throughout the magnetic circuit lets the flux density $B_{s,0}$ in the string rise to much higher values than in the iron core ($B_{s,0} \gg B_{Fe,0}$), since the string's cross sectional area is much smaller ($A_s \ll A_{Fe}$).

$$\Phi_0 = B_{s,0} \cdot A_s = B_{Fe,0} \cdot A_{Fe} \quad (2.35)$$

The diagonal dashes in the following hysteresis curve indicate the reversible permeability of a guitar string as a function of an induced static magnetic field. The reversible permeability describes the permeability for small-signal operation around a bias point (definition and details see equation 2.67). The higher the static field inside the string, the lower its reversible permeability becomes and more and more of the alternating flux will not make its way across the air gap and through the string, but take the parallel path directly through the air. In figure 2.6 this is denoted as the leakage flux Φ_l in parallel to the flux Φ_s through the string.

The following calculations and simulation prove that the actuator must operate with a magnetically saturated string ($B_{s,0} \gg B_{Fe,0}$, $\Phi_l > 0$) in order to

2. Electromagnetic Actuator and Sensor

Figure 2.7.: Guitar string hysteresis. [9]

reach the desired dynamic behaviour (maximum force acting on the string). From figure 2.7 one can read that a static flux density $B_{s,0} = 0,6 \text{ T}$ would leave enough headroom for an alternating field with amplitude $\hat{B}_{s,\sim} = 0,2 \text{ T}$ without reaching saturation within the string. As our string we assume a "Dean Markley" g-string with a diameter of $d_s = 0,432 \text{ mm}$ [6]. Its cross sectional area is:

$$A_s = \pi \cdot \left(\frac{d_s}{2}\right)^2 = \pi \cdot \left(\frac{0,432 \text{ mm}}{2}\right)^2 = 1,466 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \quad (2.36)$$

Hence, the static flux Φ_0 throughout the magnetic circuit must be

$$\Phi_0 = B_{s,0} \cdot A_s = 0,6 \text{ T} \cdot 1,466 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 = 8,794 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ Vs} \quad (2.37)$$

The coil is assumed to be wound around a cylinder of length $l_{cyl} = 1,5 \text{ cm}$ and a diameter of $d_{cyl} = 5 \text{ mm}$. The total winding thickness is set to $2,5 \text{ mm}$. Using enameled copper wire with a diameter of $d = 0,15 \text{ mm}$ the number of turns is calculated to $N = 1667$ windings, using a total wire length of $l = 62,33 \text{ m}$ (calculated with an Octave script, see appendix A). In order

2.1. Model of an Electromagnetic Transducer

to allow the string to vibrate freely, the air gaps are defined to a length of $x_0 = 1,5 \text{ mm}$. The inductance L_c and series resistance R_c of the coil result to:

$$L_c = \frac{\mu_0 N^2 A}{2x_0} = \frac{4\pi \cdot 10^{-7} \frac{\text{Vs}}{\text{Am}} 1667^2 \pi \left(\frac{5\text{mm}}{2}\right)^2}{2 \cdot 1,5 \text{ mm}} = 22,86 \text{ mH} \quad (2.38)$$

$$R_c = \frac{\rho \cdot l}{\pi \left(\frac{d}{2}\right)^2} = \frac{17,3 \cdot 10^{-9} \Omega\text{m} \cdot 62,33 \text{ m}}{\pi \left(\frac{0,15\text{mm}}{2}\right)^2} = 61,02 \Omega \quad (2.39)$$

The calculated values yield a transducer constant of:

$$\alpha = \frac{N\Phi_0}{x_0} = \frac{1667 \cdot 8,794 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ Vs}}{1,5 \text{ mm}} = 0,09773 \frac{\text{Vs}}{\text{m}} \quad (2.40)$$

The mass m of the string can be calculated from the mass per unit length taken from [6]:

$$m = 1,14 \cdot 10^{-3} \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}} \cdot 0,64 \text{ m} = 7,296 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg} \quad (2.41)$$

With $\omega_0 = \sqrt{s/m}$ and the frequency of the open g-string, $f_0 = 196 \text{ Hz}$, the stiffness s computes to:

$$s = (2\pi f_0)^2 \cdot m = (2\pi 196 \text{ Hz})^2 \cdot 7,296 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg} = 1106,51 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{m}} \quad (2.42)$$

Values in this order of magnitude can be confirmed experimentally by placing a known weight (known gravitational force) on the string and measuring its displacement. The string's stiffness increases towards the bridge where it is pinched off. Obviously, the measurement should be made at the spot where the actuator will be placed. Placing the actuator coil at 15 cm distance to the bridge allows good efficiency when trying to initiate vibrations. If the actuator would be placed close to the bridge, one could excite the harmonic spectrum more equally (increased linearity), but the

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high stiffness makes the system way to slow.

The damping coefficient R_m can be determined if the decay constant δ is known. Therefore one measures the time $t_d = 3/\delta$ that corresponds to a relative decrease in amplitude to a level of about 5% of the initial amplitude:

$$e^{-\delta t_d} = e^{-3} \approx 5\% \quad (2.43)$$

A practical way to measure the decay time t_d is to hook up the output of the electric guitar to a voltmeter. The moment one plucks the guitar string a stopwatch timer should be started. It is stopped when the voltage has decreased to 5% of the initial value. With the measured time t_d , the decay constant δ and finally the damping coefficient R_m was calculated [8].

$$t_d = 5,8 \text{ s} \rightarrow \delta = \frac{3}{t_d} = 0,52 \frac{1}{\text{s}} \quad (2.44)$$

$$R_m = 2 \cdot m \cdot \delta = 2 \cdot 7,296 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ kg} \cdot 0,52 \frac{1}{\text{s}} = 7,5 \cdot 10^{-4} \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{s}} \quad (2.45)$$

The mechanical impedances are converted into electrical ones via the transducer constant:

$$R = \frac{\alpha^2}{R_m} = 12,73 \Omega \quad L = \frac{\alpha^2}{s} = 8,63 \mu\text{H} \quad C = \frac{m}{\alpha^2} = 76,39 \text{ mF} \quad (2.46)$$

The current amplitude \hat{I}_{\sim} in order to get the desired alternating flux density of amplitude $\hat{B}_{s,\sim} = 0,2 \text{ T}$ can be ascertained given the relationship between the inductance L_c and flux Φ .

$$\frac{\hat{B}_{s,\sim}}{B_{s,0}} = \frac{0,2 \text{ T}}{0,6 \text{ T}} = \frac{1}{3} \rightarrow \hat{\Phi}_{\sim} = \frac{\Phi_0}{3} \quad (2.47)$$

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Figure 2.8.: SPICE circuit simulation of the actuator model.

$$\hat{\Phi}_{\sim} = \frac{\hat{I}_{\sim} \cdot L_c}{N} \rightarrow \hat{I}_{\sim} = \frac{N \cdot \hat{\Phi}_{\sim}}{L_c} = \frac{N \cdot \Phi_0}{3 \cdot L_c} = \frac{1667 \cdot 8,79 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ Vs}}{3 \cdot 22,86 \text{ mH}} = 2,14 \text{ mA} \quad (2.48)$$

With the acquired values one can now run a SPICE simulation (figure 2.8) of the electrical actuator model. The signal generator's voltage is set to $U = 145 \text{ mV}$ which gives the desired input current with an amplitude of $\hat{I}_{\sim} \approx 2,14 \text{ mA}$. The frequency is adjusted to $f = 196,018 \text{ Hz}$, because of rounded component values for C and L .

In figure 2.9 the transient oscillation of the current I_L (corresponding to the force at the spring) is displayed. The peak value can be read as $\hat{I}_L = 22,54 \text{ mA}$.

With the applied force-current analogy, this yields the following peak displacement:

$$\hat{F} = \alpha \cdot \hat{I}_L = 0,09773 \frac{\text{N}}{\text{A}} \cdot 22,54 \text{ mA} = 2,20 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N} \quad (2.49)$$

$$\hat{x} = \frac{F}{s} = \frac{2,20 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N}}{1106,51 \text{ N/m}} = 1,99 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m} = 1,99 \mu\text{m} \quad (2.50)$$

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Figure 2.9.: Transient state simulation of the actuator model.

Operating the system with the string unsaturated results in only $1,99 \mu\text{m}$ string displacement. A strong vibration has an amplitude of about $0,75 \text{ mm}$ (in the spot where the actuator is meant to be placed). This factor of 10^3 cannot be reached within the boundaries of a non-saturated string, which proves the claim proposed earlier in this subsection.

Despite the saturated string, the functional principal remains unchanged. Applying the strong, magnetizing DC field serves as a linearization and the alternating force will still be proportional to the alternating flux/current. Additionally, the transducer constant is still linearly proportional to the number of windings, which is justified in the following. Therefore, one has to revisit the origin of the transducer equation, the formula describing the force on the boundary surfaces.

$$F = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} A = \frac{\Phi^2}{2\mu_0 A} \quad (2.51)$$

The derivation of it (equation 2.6) is based on the fact that moving the armature by dl requires a force F that is proportional to the change of magnetic energy dW_{mag} .

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$$dW_{mag} = w_{mag} \cdot dV = F \cdot dl \quad (2.52)$$

In case of a small air gap between the core's and armature's cross sectional area, the flux density B and thus the energy density $w_{mag} = B^2/2\mu_0$ will be roughly constant in each point of the enclosed air volume. Only in this case, the above relation leads to the compact formula for the magnetic force. With a relatively small string surface and leakage flux, the B-field is no longer constant and the formula can no longer be applied. To determine the magnetic energy stored within the air volume between core and string, one would need to solve the following integral:

$$W_{mag} = \iiint_V w_{mag} dV = \iiint_V \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0} dV \quad (2.53)$$

Equally, the change in magnetic energy dW_{mag} when moving the string would require this integral to be solved. Nonetheless, the energy density will always be given by $w_{mag} = B^2/2\mu_0$ and thus the force maintains its proportionality to B^2 :

$$F_{sat} \sim B^2 \quad (2.54)$$

From now on, one can follow through on the derivation and replace the flux density with the field strength H by applying Ampere's law. For a saturated string, the field strength will not vanish inside the string, but always be proportional to N .

$$H \sim N \cdot I \rightarrow F_{sat} \sim N^2 I^2 \quad (2.55)$$

As mentioned, the linearization happens as in unsaturated operation ($I = I_0 + I_{\sim}$) and the bias current I_0 can be replaced by a term inversely proportional to N (see equation 2.11).

$$F_{\sim,sat} \sim N^2 I_0 I_{\sim} \text{ with } I_0 \sim \frac{1}{N} \rightarrow F_{\sim,sat} \sim N \cdot I_{\sim} \quad (2.56)$$

One finds that the transducer constant α_{sat} , describing the relation between force and current for saturated operation, is still proportional to N .

Because of the more complex field flow in guitar applications, the presented

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electrical two-port model can't be used for quantitative simulations. Extending the presented model to incorporate the significant leakage flux would go beyond the scope of this thesis. Nonetheless, the model proved very valuable for the transducer design and the analysis of the closed loop system (chapter 3).

2.2. Actuator

This section is dedicated to the design and evaluation of the magnetic string actuator. The goal is an actuator that excites the string's vibration quickly to enable intuitive dynamic control of a musical note. Choosable parameters in the design are:

- (1) The wire diameter, which affects the number of windings as well as the current capacity
- (2) The core and magnet material and their levels of polarization
- (3) The core's geometry

The following subsection investigates the influence of those parameters on actuator efficiency.

2.2.1. Design

Number of Windings

The force's amplitude \hat{F}_{sat} will now be analyzed regarding the number of windings N and the electrical power P being supplied.

$$\hat{F}_{sat} \sim N \cdot \hat{I} \quad (2.57)$$

First, the current amplitude \hat{I} must be expressed in terms of the power P and the absolute impedance $Z = |\underline{Z}|$.

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$$P = \frac{1}{2} \hat{U} \hat{I} = \frac{1}{2} \hat{I}^2 Z \rightarrow \hat{I} = \sqrt{\frac{2P}{Z}} \quad (2.58)$$

Since the actuator is driven with the resonance frequency f_0 of the string, the impedance Z simplifies accordingly:

$$\underline{Z} = \underline{Z}_c + \underline{Z}_{RLC} = R_c + j\omega_0 L_c + R \rightarrow Z = \sqrt{(R_c + R)^2 + (\omega_0 L_c)^2} \quad (2.59)$$

Plugging these expressions into equation 2.57 yields:

$$\hat{F}_{sat} \sim N \cdot \hat{I} = N \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2P}{Z}} = N \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2P}{\sqrt{(R_c + R)^2 + (\omega_0 L_c)^2}}} \quad (2.60)$$

If we double the number of windings, the wire length and thus the series resistance of the coil R_c will approximately double. The inductance of the coil L_c is proportional to N^2 . The resistance $R = \alpha_{sat}^2 / R_m$, with $\alpha_{sat} \sim N$, is also proportional to N^2 .

$$R_c \sim N \quad L_c \sim N^2 \quad R \sim N^2 \quad (2.61)$$

Looking at equation 2.60 we can distinguish between two cases:

(1) $\omega_0 L \ll R_c, R \ll R_c$:

For low resonance frequencies ω_0 (fundamental frequencies, "open" guitar strings) and small values of α_{sat} the series resistance of the coil R_c determines the impedance. The force is proportional to the square root of N as R_c is proportional to N .

$$\hat{F}_{sat} \sim N \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2P}{\sqrt{R_c^2}}} \sim N \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2P}{\sqrt{N^2}}} = \sqrt{N} \cdot \sqrt{2P} \quad (2.62)$$

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(2) $\omega_0 L \gg R_c$ or $R \gg R_c$:

For high resonance frequencies ω_0 (especially overtones) or large values of α_{sat} the impedance becomes proportional to N^2 . The force is then independent of N .

$$\hat{F}_{sat} \sim N \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2P}{\sqrt{R^2 + (\omega_0 L_c)^2}}} \sim N \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2P}{\sqrt{N^4}}} = \sqrt{2P} \quad (2.63)$$

These results suggest that, for low frequencies f_0 , one gains efficiency to a certain number of N , until R determines the impedance ($\alpha_{sat} \sim N$). In fact, the energy conversion efficiency is defined as the ratio between the useful power output and the total power input.

$$\eta = \frac{P_{use}}{P_{in}} \quad (2.64)$$

In terms of the string actuator, the useful power is the mechanical power $P_{mech} = F \cdot v$ moving the string. In the analogous electrical circuit, this corresponds to the power at $Z_{RLC}(\omega_0) = R$ which is given by the product $P_R = U_R \cdot I$. With the input power $P_{in} = U \cdot I$ one gets

$$\eta = \frac{P_{use}}{P_{in}} = \frac{U_R \cdot I}{U \cdot I} = \frac{U_R}{U} = \frac{R}{Z} = \frac{R}{\sqrt{(R_c + R)^2 + (\omega_0 L_c)^2}} \quad (2.65)$$

Considering the two cases mentioned, the above suggestion can be confirmed.

(1) $Z \sim N$: $\rightarrow \eta \sim \frac{N^2}{N} = N$

(2) $Z \sim N^2$: $\rightarrow \eta$ independent of N .

In fact, the two observations can be connected through

$$P_{use} = F \cdot v = \frac{F^2}{R_m} \sim \frac{\sqrt{N^2}}{R_m} = \frac{N}{R_m} \text{ for case (1)} \quad (2.66)$$

Translating these insights into a design guideline would be to guarantee enough windings, so that the proportionality for case (1) is utilized. Actually these results come handy, since the current is limited by the maximum output current of the operational amplifier driving the actuator. By increasing the number of windings N , one can further enlarge the force exerted on the string ($F \sim \alpha \sim N$), provided that also the voltage is increased to compensate for the higher impedance Z . This is mentioned, as experiments showed that the supply voltage could have been further increased, while the current was already limited by the operational amplifier.

When working with high output current amplifiers ($I_{out,max} > 100$ mA), the coil's wire with its given current-carrying capacity can become the limitation. The current-carrying capacity describes the RMS electric current that a wire can carry without getting damaged by exceeding the material specific temperature limit. The larger the cross sectional area of a wire, the higher the current-carrying capacity.

Core Material and Polarization

The permanent magnet is made of magnetically hard material and provides the system with a roughly constant biasing magnetic field. The rest of the core should be magnetically soft material to minimize hysteretic losses. For high frequencies (overtones) eddy current losses have to be taken into account. Soft ferrites (electrically nonconductive) present an option to prevent eddy current losses and thus a damping of high overtones.

As for the guitar string, the reversible permeability of the core and magnet will determine their reluctances concerning alternating fields. Figure 2.10 shows the difference between the differential permeability and the reversible permeability. The differential permeability is equivalent to the slope of the hysteresis curve. By contrast, the reversible permeability μ_{rev} is defined as the limit of the ratio $\Delta B/\Delta H$ in small-signal operation. [9]

$$\mu_{rev} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \lim_{\Delta H \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta B}{\Delta H} \quad (2.67)$$

The stronger the underlying static magnetic field, the lower the reversible permeability. Figure 2.11 shows the reversible susceptibility χ_{rev} (normalized

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Figure 2.10.: The reversible permeability is smaller than the differential permeability. [9]

by the initial value χ_I) as a function of the relative polarization.

For steel, Zollner[9] measured an initial value of $\chi_I \approx 60$, which is a lot less than the typical values given for the differential magnetic susceptibility of steel ($\approx 10^2 - 10^4$). Nonetheless, compared to air ($\chi \approx 0$), this still means high permeability. In fact, not much of the core's reversible permeability has to be given up in the design of a guitar string actuator, because of a different limitation. The static flux should not exceed a level where the field-parallel component of the string's vibration is detuned noticeably. The reason for the detuning is that the magnetic field acts as a negative stiffness, pulling the string towards the magnet against the string's mechanical stiffness. Superimposed with the unaffected field-orthogonal component of vibration, slow amplitude variations (beats) become audible [9]. Moreover, in [9] Zollner gives a value of 200 mT for the flux density measured at the surface of a guitar string in 2 mm distance of a typical guitar cylinder magnet. Own experiments with such magnets show strong beats when brought as close as 2 mm to the string. One can conclude that the static flux density must rather be lower than 200 mT (≈ 100 mT). Given the effective surface of a g-string passing along a cylindrical magnet of 5 mm diameter ($A_{\text{eff}} \approx 3,4 \text{ mm}^2$), one can estimate the magnetic flux $\Phi_{0,\text{max}}$.

$$\Phi_{0,\text{max}} = 100 \text{ mT} \cdot 3,4 \text{ mm}^2 = 3,4 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ Vs} \quad (2.68)$$

Figure 2.11.: Relative reversible susceptibility. [9]

For comparison, this is about 3,9 times the static flux that was calculated for unsaturated operation (equation 2.37). Inside the core, the flux density will be a lot lower.

$$B_{0,core} = \frac{\Phi_{0,max}}{A_{core}} = \frac{3,4 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{Vs}}{\pi(5 \text{ mm}/2)^2} = 17,3 \text{ mT} \quad (2.69)$$

Considering that even soft ferrite materials reach polarization values between 0,3 and 0,5 Tesla (steel up to 2 Tesla [5]), this equals a relative polarization of only $J_{rel} = 17,3 \text{ mT}/0,3 \text{ T} = 0,058$ in the worst case and hence a reversible susceptibility close to the initial value.

Core Geometry

In the following, design ideas concerning the core's geometry shall be discussed. Until now, a "U"-shaped circuit like in figure 2.6 was assumed. Despite the saturated string, the overall magnetic reluctance of the circuit should be as low as possible to guarantee optimal power efficiency. Indeed,

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Figure 2.12.: Actuator with two parallel pathways.

the reluctance of the circuit can be reduced by adding a second, identical pathway for the magnetic flux. From electrical circuits it is known that a parallel connection of two identical resistors $R_1 = R_2$ will result in half the resistance.

$$R_1 \parallel R_2 = \frac{R_1 \cdot R_2}{R_1 + R_2} = \frac{R_1^2}{2R_1} = \frac{R_1}{2} \quad \text{with } R_2 = R_1 \quad (2.70)$$

This leads to the layout for the string actuator seen in figure 2.12.

Figure 2.13 shows the equivalent circuit diagrams for both core shapes, where R_a denotes the reluctance of the air gaps and R_s corresponds to the string's reluctance.

As the core's level of polarization is low, its reluctance is negligible. The magnetomotive force Θ is supposed to be constant, thus two different fluxes Φ_1 and Φ_2 will result.

$$R_U = R_a + R_s + R_a \quad (2.71)$$

$$R_E = R_a + (R_s + R_a) \parallel (R_s + R_a) = R_a + \frac{R_s + R_a}{2} < R_U \quad (2.72)$$

Figure 2.13.: Magnetic circuit of the "U"- and "E"-shaped core.

Figure 2.14.: Simplified field pattern for a cylindrical magnet. [9]

$$\Phi_1 = \frac{\Theta}{R_U} < \frac{\Theta}{R_E} = \Phi_2 \quad (2.73)$$

This yields that by using the "E"-shaped core we can reduce power consumption and get the same alternating magnetic flux actuating the guitar string. Figures 2.14 and 2.15 further illustrate the concept. Bringing a cylindrical pickup magnet into proximity of a guitar string results in a symmetrical field (fig. 2.14).

By moving a tiny coil along the string (voltage is induced), Zollner[9] measured values for the flux density inside the guitar string in such an arrangement (fig 2.15).

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Figure 2.15.: Measured flux density inside the guitar string for two magnet distances. [9]

At a distance of about 6 mm from the center, the string's polarization reaches its maximum value. Not later than there, the superimposed alternating flux leaves the string and flows back through the air. It makes sense to position the outer arms of the "E" core at this distance. Bringing the outer arms closer results in a magnetic short circuit and minimizes the coil's space. Based on the presented observations, practical implementations of guitar string actuators have been built and will be discussed throughout the following subsection.

2.2.2. Experiment and Evaluation

The first experiment evaluates the theoretical results concerning the number of windings. Therefore three actuator coils with winding numbers $N_1 < N_2 < N_3$ have been wound around cylindrical cores of nickel-plated steel. A strong neodymium permanent magnet was attached to the bottom of each core. The cylindrical cores were taken from a guitar pickup and thus they did fit well onto standard pickup flatwork that was mounted onto a stratocaster pickguard (figure 2.16).

The air gap between actuator and string was adjusted to $x_0 = 2$ mm for each

Figure 2.16.: Coil with cylindrical steel core and neodymium magnet.

measurement. The driving signal was a sine wave obtained from a signal generator and adjusted in amplitude U_{rms} to ensure equal power inputs P_{in} . The frequency of the signal was adjusted to the current resonance frequency of the used b-string ($f_0 \approx 246,9$ Hz), keeping measurement inequalities as minimal as possible. Table 2.1 shows measurement data like the winding resistances R_c , copper wire diameter d and the measured peak displacement \hat{x} . Figure 2.17 shows the three different coils. A significant difference between the coil with N_1 windings and the coil with N_2 windings was measurable even with a standard ruler. The difference between N_2 and N_3 was not significant enough to be measured with a ruler and probably within the measurement error regarding the match of actuator signal frequency and resonance frequency of the string. Nonetheless, the clear difference between a low number of windings (N_1) and a higher number (N_2, N_3) confirms the theoretical results presented in the previous subsection.

The second series of measurements investigated three different core geometries. There was no measurable increase in efficiency comparing the proposed "E"-shaped core to a "U" or "I"-shaped core (figure 2.18).

However, later measurements concerning the influence of the core geometry on the sensor function showed that there is an increased inductance with the "E"-shaped core. This proves that the "E"-core does lower the magnetic reluctance in the magnetic circuit (more iron, less air). The increase in

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	R_c	d	x_0	U_{rms}	I_{rms}	P_{in}	\hat{x}
unit	Ω	mm	mm	V	mA	mW	mm
N_1	10,5	0,15	2	0,643	49,50	31,83	0,4
N_2	25,4	0,15	2	1,163	27,35	31,81	0,5
N_3	740	0,063	2	5,993	5,34	32,00	0,5

Table 2.1.: Measurement results for the three actuator coils ($N_1 < N_2 < N_3$)

Figure 2.17.: Comparison between coils with $N_1 < N_2 < N_3$ windings (from left to right).

Figure 2.18.: Comparison of "I", "U"- and "E"-shaped core geometry (from left to right).

actuator efficiency by using an "E"-shaped core might just be too low to be measured with the applied methods.

2.3. Sensor

The magnetic sensor plays the important role of providing the electronics with an electrical signal proportional to the string's velocity of vibration. The goal of the design is that even subtle string vibrations are transduced into signals above the noise floor that can be amplified into maximum actuating signals.

2.3.1. Design

Magnetic Saturation of the Guitar String

Same as for the actuator, one can ask the question if it is beneficial for the sensor to operate with a saturated, fully magnetized string. Zollner carried out measurements on the relation of the induced voltage as a function of the magnet's distance to the string. Therefore he started with a magnet-string distance of 2 mm, reduced to 1 mm and went back to 2 mm distance. From figure 2.19 one can identify two different voltage levels for the same distance of 2 mm. This is because the string is left with a higher level of polarization once the magnet has been as close as 1 mm distance (hysteresis). More precisely, the length of the string that reaches full polarization increases. Nonetheless, these measurements empirically prove that also the sensor must operate with a saturated string for maximum sensitivity.

A theoretical explanation can be given based on Faraday's law of induction:

$$U_{ind} = N \frac{d\Phi}{dt} \quad (2.74)$$

If we consider the string as a vibrating magnet, it becomes obvious that the larger its magnetization is, the larger the change in flux will be due to its

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Figure 2.19.: Induced voltage level as a function of the magnet-string distance.[9]

vibration. According to Faraday's law, the larger the change in flux is, the larger is the induced voltage.

Number of Windings

Concerning the number of windings, Faraday's law suggests to wind a coil with as many turns as possible, since the induced voltages of all turns add up to the voltage at the terminals of the coil. In contrast to the actuator, power observations simplify for the sensor, since its electrical (output) terminals will be buffered by an operational amplifier (high input impedance). This means there is no significant current flow that would then cause a loss due to the coil's winding resistance (that would be proportional to N). For this reason guitar pickups are wound with 5000 – 10000 turns and reach winding resistances up to 11 k Ω . [9]

Core Material and Polarization

The insights gained on the preferable core material can be transferred from the actuator to the sensor. The level of the core's polarization has the same limit, since the static magnetic field of the sensor should not significantly influence the string's vibration.

Figure 2.20.: Measurement of induced voltage for the "E"-core sensor. An EBow was placed on adjacent strings to excite the string.

Core Geometry

It is well known, that a ferromagnetic core (typically soft iron or soft ferrite) increases the inductance of a coil. As seen in the transducer model section, the less of the magnetic pathway is air, the higher the inductance (equation 2.33). One can generalize this to the idea of the least possible magnetic reluctance. As a consequence, also for the sensor an "E"-shaped core is preferable.

2.3.2. Experiment and Evaluation

The sensor experiments investigated the induced voltage considering the proposed "E"-core in comparison to the simple "I"-core. The string was excited by an EBow that was placed on adjacent strings at a specific spot to ensure equal amplitudes of vibration for both measurements (figure 2.20).

The induced voltage with the "I"-core was $U_I = 51 \text{ mV}$. The "E"-core measurement gave $U_E = 64 \text{ mV}$. This increase of 25% can be explained by an increased inductance of the "E"-core coil that is caused by the additional steel parts in the magnetic circuit that lower the overall magnetic reluctance.

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2.4. Conclusion

Through in depth study of the transducer model and electromagnetism, the influence of relevant design parameters could be determined. For the actuator, increasing the number of windings is only beneficial to a certain point, contrary to the sensor, where an increase in number of windings will increase the induced voltage in any case. Both actuator and sensor efficiency are increased if the core material has a high magnetic (reversible) permeability. Equally, the overall magnetic reluctance can be reduced by an "E"-shaped core. The DC field induced by the permanent magnet should have the highest possible value without distorting the string's vibration noticeably.

3. Feedback Loop for Amplitude Control

To actively excite or damp the vibration of the guitar string, one needs an actuating signal that contains resonating frequencies and has the correct phasing. The sensor provides a signal with matching frequencies, however, it is necessary to amplify this signal in order to effectively actuate the string. The phase shift between sensor and actuator signal distinguishes positive feedback (in phase) from negative feedback (180° phase shift). The first section of this chapter deals with deriving this claim. Hereafter, SPICE simulations are carried out (3.2) and the whole feedback system is evaluated experimentally (3.3).

3.1. Differential Equation and Phasing

With the help of the sensor and actuator circuit models, one can compose a complete electrical model of the electromechanical feedback system. Between sensor and actuator an operational amplifier is inserted. Its gain G can be either positive (non-inverting) or negative (inverting), depending on its configuration. For simplicity, the sensor and actuator are assumed to have equal transducer constants α and use the same coils (L_c, R_c). This way, both transformers implementing the transducer constant can be left away (subsection 2.1.1). Figure 3.1 depicts such a feedback circuit. All voltages and currents in the figure are denoted in small letters expressing their time dependency (apostrophes indicate time derivatives). The goal is to set up the differential equation describing the string's oscillations under the influence of the feedbacked signal.

3. Feedback Loop for Amplitude Control

Figure 3.1.: Electrical model of the feedback system.

The input impedance of an operational amplifier is so large that i_s can be neglected ($i_s \approx 0$). [3] Thus, the voltage u_s at the terminals of the sensor coil equals the voltage u at the resonant circuit ($u_s = u$). The amplifier outputs the voltage $u_a = G \cdot u_s = G \cdot u$ to the terminals of the actuator. For $|G| > 1$ this causes a current i_a through the actuator coil, equalling an external force acting on the string. The magnitude of the coil's impedance shall be denoted as $Z_c = \sqrt{R_c^2 + \omega^2 L_c^2}$. For now, its phase shifting property is assumed to be negligible.

$$i_a = \frac{u_a - u}{Z_c} = \frac{G \cdot u - u}{Z_c} = \frac{G - 1}{Z_c} \cdot u \quad (3.1)$$

To set up the differential equation, Kirchhoff's point rule (nodal rule) is applied.

$$i_R + i_C + i_L = i_a \quad (3.2)$$

$$i_R + i_C + i_L = \frac{u}{R} + C \cdot u' + i_L = i_a = \frac{G - 1}{Z_c} \cdot u \quad (3.3)$$

3.1. Differential Equation and Phasing

$$\rightarrow i_L = \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \cdot u - C \cdot u' - \frac{u}{R} = \left(\frac{G-1}{Z_c} - \frac{1}{R} \right) \cdot u - C \cdot u' \quad (3.4)$$

Furthermore, with Kirchhoff's second law ($u = u_L$) one finds

$$u = u_L = L \cdot i'_L \quad (3.5)$$

Inserting equation 3.4 into equation 3.5 yields the second-order linear ordinary differential equation.

$$u = L \cdot i'_L = L \cdot \left(\frac{G-1}{Z_c} - \frac{1}{R} \right) \cdot u' - LC \cdot u'' \quad (3.6)$$

$$LC \cdot u'' + L \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \right) \cdot u' + u = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

$$u'' + \underbrace{\frac{1}{C} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \right)}_{2\tilde{\delta}} \cdot u' + \underbrace{\frac{1}{LC}}_{\omega_0^2} u = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

In case of $\tilde{\delta} < \omega_0$ (underdamped, oscillating case) the solution of this differential equation is given by (derivation see [2]):

$$\rightarrow u(t) = A \cdot e^{-\tilde{\delta}t} \cdot \cos(\sqrt{\omega_0^2 - \tilde{\delta}^2} \cdot t + \phi_0) \quad (3.9)$$

One finds that the feedback alters the decay constant $\tilde{\delta} = \tilde{\delta}(G)$, which can be seen from the differential equation (term in front of the first derivative).

$$\tilde{\delta}(G) = \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

Depending on the gain G of the amplifier, three cases can be distinguished.

3. Feedback Loop for Amplitude Control

(1) Vibration with constant amplitude: $\tilde{\delta} = 0$

$$\tilde{\delta} = \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \right) = 0 \rightarrow G = 1 + \frac{Z_c}{R} \quad (3.11)$$

(2) Vibration with increasing amplitude: $\tilde{\delta} < 0$

$$\tilde{\delta} = \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \right) < 0 \rightarrow G > 1 + \frac{Z_c}{R} \quad (3.12)$$

(3) Vibration with decreasing amplitude: $\tilde{\delta} > 0$

$$\tilde{\delta} = \frac{1}{2C} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \right) > 0 \rightarrow G < 1 + \frac{Z_c}{R} \quad (3.13)$$

For a constant amplitude of vibration, the amplifier exactly makes up for the frictional loss of the guitar string that is inversely proportional to R ($R_m = \alpha^2/R$, subsection 2.1.1). Additionally, the impedance of the coil (Z_c) is taken into account as it limits the current i_a through the actuator.

Case (3) can be subdivided into special situations like $G = 1$, corresponding to an undriven (free) damped oscillator with decay constant $\tilde{\delta}(G = 1) = \delta = 1/(2RC)$. In this situation $u_a = G \cdot u$ equals u , the actuator current i_a and thus the externally applied force become zero. For gain values of $G < 1$ (especially large negative values) the decay constant is increased ($\tilde{\delta} > \delta$), hence the vibration will fade faster than for an undriven damped oscillator. In other words, a large non-inverting amplification ($G \gg 1$) results in positive feedback (quickly increasing amplitude). In contrast, an inverting amplification ($G \ll 0$) corresponds to negative feedback (damping).

So far, no attention was given to the fact that the inductance of the actuator coil affects the phase relation between the current i_a (proportional to the actuating force) and the current i_L (proportional to the displacement of the string). For a damped harmonic oscillator, the driving force needs to be 90° phase shifted in relation to the displacement in order to manipulate its decay constant only, while keeping the frequency of vibration unchanged

3.1. Differential Equation and Phasing

(derivation see appendix B). Combining equations 3.1 and 3.5, one finds the following relation:

$$i_a = \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \cdot u = \frac{G-1}{Z_c} \cdot L \cdot i'_L \quad (3.14)$$

The analysis is simplified by writing the equation in phasor notation:

$$\underline{I}_a = \frac{G-1}{\underline{Z}_c} \cdot \underline{U} = \frac{G-1}{R_c + j\omega L_c} \cdot L \cdot j\omega \underline{I}_L \quad (3.15)$$

One can distinguish between two cases:

(1) $R_c \ll \omega L_c$:

For high resonance frequencies ω_0 and a high inductance L_c the reactance becomes the dominant component of the impedance and shifts the currents (force and displacement) in phase, which results in altered (distorted) frequency of oscillation (appendix B).

$$\underline{I}_a = \frac{G-1}{R_c + j\omega L_c} \cdot L \cdot j\omega \underline{I}_L \approx \frac{G-1}{j\omega L_c} \cdot L \cdot j\omega \underline{I}_L = \frac{G-1}{L_c} \cdot L \cdot \underline{I}_L \quad (3.16)$$

(2) $R_c \gg \omega L_c$:

For low resonance frequencies ω_0 and a low inductance L_c the resistance becomes the dominant component of the impedance and the phasing between the currents (force and displacement) is optimal.

$$\underline{I}_a = \frac{G-1}{R_c + j\omega L_c} \cdot L \cdot j\omega \underline{I}_L \approx \frac{G-1}{R_c} \cdot L \cdot j\omega \underline{I}_L \quad (3.17)$$

3. Feedback Loop for Amplitude Control

3.2. SPICE Simulation

The described behaviour can be well tested in SPICE simulations. In fact, simulations with the electrical model of the feedback system eliminated misconceptions and inspired further research that led to setting up the above differential equation. For the following simulations we assume the same coil and guitar string (mechanical impedance) as calculated in subsection 2.1.2. For saturated operation, the simulations do not provide valid quantitative results, nonetheless the theoretical insights of this chapter (and appendix B) can be verified as the physical principals remain unchanged. The transducer constant could be arbitrarily chosen, for this simulation it is four times the one used for the unsaturated simulations in subsection 2.1.2 (the static flux is assumed to be about four times the flux as for the unsaturated example, see equation 2.68). This results in altered values for the electrical resonant circuit:

$$\alpha_{sat} = 4 \cdot 0,09773 \frac{Vs}{m} = 0,3909 \frac{Vs}{m} \quad (3.18)$$

$$R = \frac{\alpha_{sat}^2}{R_m} = 203,76 \Omega \quad L = \frac{\alpha_{sat}^2}{s} = 138,09 \mu H \quad C = \frac{m}{\alpha_{sat}^2} = 4,77 mF \quad (3.19)$$

Figure 3.2 shows a feedback system with a positive amplification implemented by a non-inverting amplifier.

The gain of the non-inverting amplifier is set to

$$G = 1 + \frac{R_1}{R_2} = 1 + \frac{100 k\Omega}{10 k\Omega} = 11 \quad (3.20)$$

With an initial value for the current i_L unequal to zero the oscillaton swells as expected (figure 3.3).

For this resonance frequency f_0 and actuator coil impedance \underline{Z}_c , the frequency of vibration f_1 is close to the unaltered resonance frequency f_0 (figure 3.4):

3.2. SPICE Simulation

Figure 3.2.: SPICE circuit simulation of a positive feedback system.

Figure 3.3.: Transient state analysis of the positive feedback system (seen is current i_L proportional to the oscillator displacement).

3. Feedback Loop for Amplitude Control

Figure 3.4.: Observing the frequency of vibration for $R_c > \omega_0 L_c$.

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{138,09 \mu\text{H} \cdot 4,77 \text{ mF}}} = 196,10 \text{ Hz} \quad (3.21)$$

$$f_1 = 195,85 \text{ Hz} \quad R_c = 61,02 \Omega > \omega_0 L_c = 28,17 \Omega \quad (3.22)$$

If the resistance of the coil is set to a negligible value ($R_c = 10^{-3} \text{ n}\Omega$) and the inductance is increased to $L_c = 50 \text{ mH}$ the currents are in phase and the simulation confirms a (significant) decrease in frequency of vibration (figure 3.5).

$$f_2 = 186,97 \text{ Hz} \ll 196,10 \text{ Hz} = f_0 \quad (3.23)$$

For negative feedback, the non-inverting amplifier is replaced by an inverting amplifier (figure 3.6). The gain of the inverting amplifier is set to

$$G = -\frac{R_2}{R_1} = -\frac{1000 \text{ k}\Omega}{10 \text{ k}\Omega} = -100 \quad (3.24)$$

3.2. SPICE Simulation

Figure 3.5.: Observing the frequency of vibration for $R_c \ll \omega_0 L_c$.

Figure 3.6.: SPICE circuit simulation of a negative feedback system.

3. Feedback Loop for Amplitude Control

Figure 3.7.: Transient state analysis of the negative feedback system (seen is current i_L proportional to the oscillator displacement).

The initial condition of the current i_L is set to a value that corresponds to a significant mechanical displacement. The damping behaviour is seen in figure 3.7. For comparison the decay of the free (undriven) damped oscillator has been simulated and can be seen in figure 3.8.

3.3. Experiment and Evaluation

For the closed loop experiments the coil with the most windings (N_3 , $R_c = 740\ \Omega$) was used as a sensor coil and a coil with $R_c = 26,9\ \Omega$ operated as the actuator coil. The amplifier was built using a Texas Instruments TL972 dual operational amplifier IC (integrated circuit). The necessary bipolar power supply was achieved by two 9V batteries. Surprisingly, a single stage of amplification wasn't able to provide enough amplification of the sensor signal to sustain the string's vibrations steadily after a pluck (even with the gain set to $G_1 = 1001 = 1 + R_1/R_2 = 1 + 4,7\text{M}\Omega/4,7\text{k}\Omega$). Hence, the second operational amplifier in the TL972 IC was connected in series with an identical amplification $G_2 = G_1$. Finally, a steady and strong vibration of the string could be seen and heard (figure 3.9).

3.3. Experiment and Evaluation

Figure 3.8.: Decay of the free (undriven) damped oscillator (current i_L /oscillator displacement).

Figure 3.9.: Positive feedback sustained a strong vibration of the string.

3. Feedback Loop for Amplitude Control

The theoretical gain was

$$G = G_1 \cdot G_2 = 1001 \cdot 1001 = 1002001 \quad (3.25)$$

However, measurements in steady state did yield an amplifier input voltage (sensor output voltage) of $U_{in,rms} = 53 \text{ mV}$ corresponding to an amplifier output voltage of $U_{out,rms} = 2,329 \text{ V}$. Thus, the actual amplification (on-load operation) in steady state was $G = U_{out,rms}/U_{in,rms} = 43,94$. With an output current of $I_{out,rms} = 15,45 \text{ mA}$ the output power to sustain the vibration was

$$P = U_{out,rms} \cdot I_{out,rms} = 2,329 \text{ V} \cdot 15,45 \text{ mA} = 35,98 \text{ mW} \quad (3.26)$$

This value corresponds well to the ones measured during the actuator experiments (table 2.1).

Despite the strong vibration that could be sustained by the positive feedback loop, it required a pluck to start the swell of the vibration. The reason for that is likely that the TL972 is stated as a "very-low-noise" amplifier (the data sheet mentions an equivalent input noise level of $4 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$). To initiate a vibration by means of the feedback loop, there needs to be enough amplifier output noise being applied to the string that is then acting as a resonance filter in the loop. Using a different IC, the Texas Instruments LM386 audio amplifier, vibrations could be initiated by the feedback loop (voltage gain set to 200). Contrary to the TL972, the LM386 is not stated as a low noise amplifier. In fact, the equivalent input noise level is not even specified in the data sheet.

Finally, a negative feedback loop was set up by turning the second amplifier into an inverting one. Equally, the terminals of the actuator coil can be switched. The current will flow through the windings in opposite direction, hence producing a field of opposite direction. In the experiments with the TL972 IC, the fundamental frequency and lower harmonics could be damped, contrary to some higher harmonics that likely undergo a phase shift caused by the amplifier that is large enough to result in positive feedback again. As mentioned, the vibration of a plucked string is two-dimensional. Damping the fretboard-orthogonal vibration with a setup seen

in figure 3.9 will leave the fretboard-parallel vibration undamped. Thus, it is more difficult to damp a string than to excite or sustain a vibration (which can be well done with a one-dimensional actuating system).

3.4. Conclusion and Outlook

The phase relations for positive and negative feedback could be derived by setting up the differential equation describing the feedback system. For positive feedback, the sensor voltage should be amplified in phase, for negative feedback, a phase shift of 180° needs to be applied. Indeed, the phase of the exerted force is shifted in an undesired manner by the inductance of the actuator coil. Additionally, a real operational amplifier will introduce a phase shift to the sensor signal that needs to be taken into account.

Certainly, many improvements in performance and efficiency of the feedback system can be achieved by further experimentation and research. For example, using especially "noisy" amplifiers or introducing a noise source to the circuit are further attempts to speed up the initiation of vibrations. Furthermore, experimentation with different amplifier topologies (for example class D amplifiers) could increase efficiency.

An installed feedback system only reaches its musical potential when the feedback becomes controllable, enabling to give dynamics and life to a musical note. Therefore, a voltage-controlled amplifier needs to be introduced and addressed by a controller device like a foot pedal or a breath controller. Moreover, musical experimentation with the EBow showed big potential for the "piano-like" playing of the guitar with two independent acting hands. Since the string's vibration can be achieved by means of the magnetic driver, the plucking hand is free to play its own voice. This type of playing is not completely new, but it typically means hammering your fingers onto the fretboard (physiologically bad), resulting in rather weak vibrations. Supporting the initiation of a musical note by the magnetic driver when hammering a note and then being able to manipulate the dynamics enables new ways of interaction. The hope here is that this inspires new musical compositions and proves as a useful "extension of the instrument" rather than an "effect".

Appendix A.

Octave Script

```
clc
clear all

%coil geometry and physical constants in SI units
mu = 4*pi*10(-7); %permeability of free space
roh = 17.3 * 10(-9); %copper resistivity at 20 degrees Celsius
d = 0.00015; %copper diameter
l = 0.015; %coil length
ri= 0.005; %inner coil radius
ro = ri + 0.0025; %outer coil radius
c = ro-ri; %total winding thickness

%calculation of the number of windings N
N_e = l/d; %number of windings of one single cylindrical layer
N = N_e *(c/d) %total number of windings

%calculation of the total used wire length l_d
l1=0;
for i = 1:(c/d) %used wire length of one horizontal layer
    l1 = l1 + 2*pi*(ri+i*d-d/2);
end
l_w = l1 * N_e; %total wire length

R_c = roh * l_w/(pi*(d/2)2) %coil's winding resistance
```


Appendix B.

Damped Oscillator Feedback

In this appendix section the necessary phase shift between force and displacement in order to excite or damp the string's vibration will be derived. As with the transducer model, the string shall again be represented only by its fundamental resonance. Figure B.1 shows a damped harmonic oscillator with the displacement of the mass $x(t)$ and an externally applied force $F_{act}(t)$.

The differential equation describing the behaviour is given through Newton's second law:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= m\ddot{x} = F_{act} - sx - R_m\dot{x} \\ m\ddot{x} + R_m\dot{x} + sx &= F_{act} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

The homogeneous equation ($F_{act} = 0$) can be written in its standard form introducing the decay constant $\delta = R_m/2m$ and the resonance frequency $\omega_0 = \sqrt{s/m}$. It can be solved via an exponential approach [2]:

$$\ddot{x}_h + 2\delta\dot{x}_h + \omega_0^2 x_h = 0 \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$\rightarrow x_h(t) = A \cdot e^{-\delta t} \cdot \cos(\sqrt{\omega_0^2 - \delta^2} t + \phi_0) \quad (\text{B.3})$$

The external driving force F_{act} shall be composed of the proportional, integral and derivative function of the velocity \dot{x} . Equivalently, one can apply the

Appendix B. Damped Oscillator Feedback

Figure B.1.: Damped harmonic oscillator driven by F_{act}

derivative, proportional and second derivative function of the displacement x .

$$F_{act} = K_{DD}\ddot{x} + K_D\dot{x} + K_Px \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Plugging F_{act} into Equation B.1 gives:

$$m\ddot{x} + R_m\dot{x} + sx = K_{DD}\ddot{x} + K_D\dot{x} + K_Px \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$(m - K_{DD})\ddot{x} + (R_m - K_D)\dot{x} + (s - K_P)x = 0 \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Dividing by $(m - K_{DD})$ leads to the standard form of the homogeneous equation:

$$\ddot{x} + \frac{R_m - K_D}{m - K_{DD}}\dot{x} + \frac{s - K_P}{m - K_{DD}}x = \ddot{x} + 2\tilde{\delta}\dot{x} + \tilde{\omega}_0^2x = 0 \quad (\text{B.7})$$

The solution contains altered damping and frequency of vibration:

$$\rightarrow x(t) = A \cdot e^{-\tilde{\delta}t} \cdot \cos(\sqrt{\tilde{\omega}_0^2 - \tilde{\delta}^2}t + \phi_0) \quad (\text{B.8})$$

Applying a force in phase with the derivate or second derivative of the displacement alters the damping:

$$\tilde{\delta} = \frac{R_m - K_D}{2(m - K_{DD})} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

The undamped frequency of vibration is altered by an external force in phase with the second derivative or the displacement itself:

$$\tilde{\omega}_0 = \sqrt{\frac{s - K_P}{m - K_{DD}}} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

These equations reveal that changing the vibration's amplitude without detuning its frequency can be done by applying a force in phase with the derivative of the displacement. Moderate feedback ($K_D < R_m$) will result in a sustained decay, strong feedback ($K_D > R_m$) results in a swelling vibration since $\tilde{\delta}$ will become negative.

The guitar string signal is a sum of roughly sinusoidal harmonics. The first derivative of a sine signal equals a 90° phase shifted version.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sin(\omega t) = \cos(\omega t) \cdot \omega = \sin(\omega t + 90^\circ) \cdot \omega \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Thus, the goal is a driving force that is either $+90^\circ$ (positive feedback) or -90° (negative feedback) phase shifted in relation to the displacement of the oscillator. Imagining yourself pushing and pulling somebody on a swing can help to illustrate this fact.

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